

**ISLAMIC ARCHITECTURE OF KASHMIR UNDER SULTANS: STUDY TOMB OF
SULTAN ZAIN-UL- ABIDIN'S MOTHER**

Dr. Sabeen Ahmad Sofi, Department: History, [E-mail: sofisabeen@gmail.com](mailto:sofisabeen@gmail.com)

Dr. Mudasir Amin, Department: Economics, [E-mail-mudasireco786@gmail.com](mailto:mudasireco786@gmail.com)

Abstract; the sultans of Kashmir were great builders, as is attested by a few remnants of their constructive buildings, visible in the valley of Kashmir. This period was witnessed the development of a new religious philosophy of Sufism, but the monotheistic philosophy of Islam also gave new dimensions to various forms of art and architecture in the Kashmir valley. The sultans of Kashmir choose different types of style, such as idiom, building material and decoration for their architecture as compared to earlier Hindu and Buddhist architecture. The plinth and the enclosure wall of the tomb are of an ancient Hindu temple, in the form of a hemisphere resting on a cylindrical drum, the first of its kind in India. The most notable development in brick architecture under sultans was however, the introduction of double dome by sultan Zainul abidins quite successfully in his mother's tomb. A peculiar feature of the brick buildings of this period is that they are studded with glazed, moulded or enameled bricks or tiles like the Timurid monuments of Samarkand and Bukhara.

Key words: Tomb, Architecture, buried, structure, sultan, Badshah, plinth,

Introduction: tomb of sultan Zain-ul-Abidin's mother is one of the oldest Muslim building's in Srinagar, is situated immediately below the Zaina Kadal which was founded by sultan Zain-ul-Abidin. Zain-ul-Abidin's mother whose name was Mera Devi¹, was buried in the bigger structure. The mausoleum of Zain-ul-Abidin's mother is in the midst of a graveyard called as Mazar-i-Salatin. The tomb is a marvelous brick structure stands on the plinth, which is square in plan with rectangular projections at the four corners, originally belonged to an ancient temple, but they differs among themselves regarding the adjustment of the plinth to an Islamic type building. Percy Brown says that the plinth was undisturbed and the plan of the Hindu building was a square with rectangular offsets projecting diagonally from each of its angles, a formation which it may be observed, made it less difficult to convert into a structure resembling the conventional Muslim tomb². Similar view is quoted by W.H. Nicholas, says the torus moulding of this plinth is practically complete, and from the way the stone is jointed at the angles on the plan, it is quite certain that the plinth has never been appreciably disturbed³. The angles of the plinth were cut off and replaced by rectangular projections, so that a Muslim tomb could be erected over it. Based on a similar pattern, the building consists of a single centrally-situated chamber with projections recessed internally at the angles. It is surmounted by four cupolas of equal size resting on the rectangular projections and a large towering dome attached to these⁴. The tomb which follows the same plan as the plinth is entirely built of glazed bricks secured with the help of lime mortar and is purely Islamic in details, the use of glazed bricks in the near contemporary architecture of Multan and Sindh. It is most probably because of the reason that the brick architecture of both Kashmir and Punjab originated under the influence of Persian and central asia⁵. The important features of the tomb are the glazed and moulded blue bricks, which are studded, at intervals in the exterior walls, the semi-circular brick projections on the drum of the main dome and the mould, string courses and sunk panels on the drums of

the cupolas⁶. Each wall of this structure has an archway set into it and there are the remains of fluting and arcading in the tall drums of the domes, while the inner doorway seems to have been an attempt at a rare type of horse-shoe arch. The design and execution of this tomb implies Persian influence⁷. The principle feature of the tomb is its shape and volume and the central dome of the tomb is composed of two separate shells, outer and inner with an appreciable gap in between. Such a structural composition appears to be the earliest manifestation of double dome in india⁸. On north side of tomb the visible portion of the plinth is about 1.5 meter in height. The entrance of the mausoleum occurs in the projection on the North West. The remaining projections are closed and form small chamber opening into the octagonal chambers in the centre. Inside the tomb there is an iron chain, hanging from an iron plate and suggestive of a Hindu influence⁹.

In the open court to the north of the tomb is situated the tomb of sultan Zain-ul-Abidin and surrounded by an enclosure wall with a horse-shoe arched gateway. This wall like that of the shankaracharya temple, has been the object of much controversy. Cunningham and Cole ascribed it to a date as early as the 4th-5th century A.D¹⁰. Their view point was contested by Fergusson, who on the strength of the resemblance of the miniature arches which decorate this wall to similar decorative features in Muslim Architecture, maintained that it was built by the Muslims themselves at the time they erected the mausoleum¹¹. But it is probable that Cunningham and Cole, who actually saw it, were nearer the truth than Fergusson, who judged only from photographs. Moreover proof of its Hindu origin is the number of carved stone still found round the site, which bear sculptured reliefs of Hindu deities.

In the graveyard to the west of the Mausoleum is a tomb stone, over which is engraved inscription in Persian to the memory of Mirza Haider Gurgan, the cousin of Babar, who made his 1st raid into kashmir from Turkistan and occupied it a 2nd time in the name of Humayun, during the latter's exile from Hindustan. The following inscription on his tomb stone gives as:

Shah Gurgan Mirza Haidar akhir
Ba mulke shahadat zadah kus-I shahi
Qaza-e Ilahi chunin bud-o tarikh
Shuda bahr-I vaslash, Qaza-e Ilahi

Translation: at last the king Mirza Haidar Gurgan beat his royal drum (to announce his departure) for the realm of martyrdom. Such was the will of God and even the date of his union (with God) is contained in (the phrase) "will of God".

Conclusion: The advent of Muslim period opened a new epoch in the history of Kashmir. The sultans of Kashmir were great builders, but with the passage of time, nothing remains of their works except the tomb of sultan Zainul abidins mother, the tomb of sayed Mohammad Madani and the khanqah of shah Hamdan. They gave to the world, what is known as the wooden architecture of Kashmir, which has a distinct style of its own. Muslims in Kashmir were in the beginning far too few to initiate an architecture of their own. All that they did was to utilize the materials of disused Hindu temples for construction of their mosques. The result was peculiar. The important land mark in the development of Architecture in Kashmir can be properly assessed against the historical events specified above. Great artistic heights were achieved because of a receptive and a reactive mind to the ever changing pattern of Nature's enchanting bounties, which attract thousands to this part of India. Of all the arts kashmiris were proficient in building activities, the remnants of which stand a testimony to the heights which have singled

them out in this field also. In short the local architects, artisans and masons who had the know-how of making the double domes constructed the domes of Badshah tomb.

Ground Plan of Tomb

Tomb of Zain-ul-Abidin's Mother

References:

1. Jonaraja, Rajatarangini, tr. Eng. J.C, Dutt, as kings of Kashmir, verse 715, pp. 55-56
2. Percy Brown, Indian Architecture (Islamic Period), India 1981, p. 82
3. W.H. Nicholls, Muhammadan Architecture in Kashmir, ASI Annual Report (1906-1907), P. 161
4. Badruddin Muqem, Holly sites of Jammu and Kashmir in the surroundings of Mighty Himalayas, Srinagar, 2011, p. 72
5. Ahmad Nabi Khan, Islamic Architecture in South Asia (Pakistan-India-Bangladesh), Karachi, 2003, p. 38
6. G.M.D. Sufi, Kashir (Being a History of Kashmir), vol. 2, New Delhi 1974, p. 506
7. R.C. Kak, Ancient Monuments of Kashmir, New Delhi, 2000, p. 81.
8. R.C. Agrawal, Kashmir and its monumental glory, New Delhi, 1998, p. 175
9. N.K. Zutshi, Sultan zain-ul-Abidin of An Age of Enlightenment, Srinagar, 2012, p. 200
10. H.H. Cole, Illustrations of Ancient Buildings in Kashmir, Srinagar, 2008, p. 8.
11. James Fergusson, History of Indian and Eastern Architecture, Vol.1, London, 1910, p. 253